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BEST PRACTICES FOR REVIEWING MANUSCRIPTS IN ENGINEERING EDUCATION RESEARCH

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ABSTRACT

In this session, participants will consider best practices and generate practical advice for reviewing manuscripts in the field of engineering education research. Improving one's skills to review effectively is a wise investment. Reviewers can stay in tune with the field and acquire insights to improve their own writing. Understanding the editorial process from the inside is also helpful when taking one's own manuscript from submission to successful publication.

Workshop facilitators are a team of editors of four leading journals:

- European Journal of Engineering Education (SEFI)
- IEEE Transactions on Education
- Journal of Engineering Education (ASEE)
- Australasian Journal of Engineering Education (AAEE)

We welcome both experienced and new reviewers, especially doctoral students in engineering education research.

Participants will be able to:

- Explain different quality criteria for scholarship in engineering education, and how to apply them
- Highlight particular aspects of a manuscript that a reviewer should consider

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- Discuss how reviews can support editors in making fair decisions and authors in improving their manuscripts
- Consider how reviewers can spend their own time wisely

Introductions

- Brief introductions: participants and session leaders. [5 minutes]
- The journals: aims and scope, review criteria and review process. [15 minutes]

Group activity

- Make a poster in groups of four: “Advice for reviewers”. [30 minutes]
- Vernissage (hanging the posters).

Synthesis

- Plenary discussion of results. Editors’ picks. Collected wisdom and conclusions. [25 minutes]

Participants can sign up for receiving documentation from session, and volunteer as reviewers for the journals.